

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping pattern involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N, 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names – not trade names – for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

Panke, a promising rice variety for rainfed uplands in West Bengal

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A direct-seeded trial of semitall variety Panke in different agroclimatic areas of West Bengal (India) was conducted in 1982-84. Soil pH of test locations varied from 5.4 to 8.1. Soil types included silty clay, clay loam, and sandy loam, representing Terai, alluvial, and red-lateritic zones.

Panke consistently performed well at Beldanga, Malda, Krishnagore, Majhian, and Nalhati (see table). In 1982, it was among the five top yielders in 5 of 6 sites; in 1983-84, it produced either more grain than or as much as the highest yielders in most of the test sites. The maximum yield recorded for Panke was 5.1 t/ha at Malda in 1984.

Panke has good panicle weight and 145 to 150 short bold grains in each panicle. The seeds have a dormancy period of about 45 d. Test weight is 18.5 g. Panke matures in 100-105 d. *ℓ*

Grain yield of Panke in multilocal trials, West Bengal.

Test site	Yield (t/ha)					
	Panke			Dular (trial check)		
	1982	1983	1984	1982	1983	1984
Hathwara	0.5	1.9	–	1.4	1.2	–
Malda	2.1	1.6	5.1	1.2	1.0	2.8
Beldanga	3.6	3.6	3.1	2.3	2.3	3.7
Krishnagore	0.9	1.9	2.4	0.8	2.0	2.7
Majhian	2.9	2.9	2.7	2.0	1.4	2.5
Nalhati	2.7	1.7	2.7	2.3	1.8	1.3
Chinsurah	–	2.0	2.0	–	0.8	1.2
Mohitnagar	–	1.3	0.9	–	2.4	0.7
Bankura	–	3.6	1.7	–	2.8	1.8
Mean	2.1	2.3	2.6	1.6	1.8	2.1

ASD16, a new short-duration rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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The elite rice culture ASD19789, isolated from the cross ADT31/CO 39, was released in Jan 1986 as rice variety ASD16 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu. It is suitable for cultivation during the first crop season (Apr-Jul sowing) as an alternate to TKM9, ADT31, ADT36, CO 37, IET1444, and IR50.

Mean yield was 5.6 t/ha, 14.3% more than for TKM9, ADT31, and ADT36 (Table 1). Overall performance in research station trials, multilocation trials, adaptive research trials, national trials under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, and international trials under the International Rice Testing Program was also good. Yield increased 4.3-26.3% over ADT31, ADT36, CO 37, IET1444, IR36, and IR50 and straw yield increased 2.2-59.6% (Table 2).

Total biological yield was 13.6 t/ha (5.6 t grain and 8.0 t straw) and potential grain yield was 9.8 t/ha.

ASD16 is a semidwarf (93 cm) and nonlodging rice. Its total duration

Table 1. Performance of ASD16 at Ambasamuduram, India, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle wt (g)
ASD16	5.6	114	93	7.5	1.71
ADT31	4.9	112	88	7.8	1.50
ADT36	4.9	115	89	8.9	1.32
TKM9	4.9	112	87	9.0	1.33

ranged from 110 to 115 d, averaging 114 d. Its grain is short and bold with white rice. The 1,000-grain weight is 24.2 g. Its high yield potential is mainly due to a panicle weight of 1.71 g.

The variety has good response to the application of high levels of N, up to 120 kg/ha. Rice recovery was 70.2-71.3%. Protein content of the kernel is

10.25%, higher than TKM9 (6.9%) and ADT36 (8.53%). Cooking quality is highly preferred, with an overall taste score of more than 75%.

ASD16 possesses moderate resistance to narrow brown leaf spot and sheath rot under controlled conditions and to brown planthopper biotype 1 in the field.

Table 2. Overall performance of ASD16 in state, national, and international trials. Tamil Nadu, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
ASD16	4.8	9.1
TKM9	5.0	8.7
ADT31	4.6	8.9
ADT36	4.5	7.9
CO 37	4.1	8.8
IET1444	3.8	5.7
IR36	3.8	—
IR50	4.6	7.4

Seedlings are flexible up to 35 d. In addition to suitability for the first crop season, ASD16 also can be sown in Nov or in Dec-Jan. ☞

Performance of new short-duration rice cultivars at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute

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The performance of 36 early-maturing IRRI cultivars was assessed in Jun-Jul 1983 at TNRRI. ADT36, TKM9, IR50, and IR60 were used as controls in a randomized block design replicated twice.

Seeds were sown in elevated nursery beds and 24-d-old seedlings were planted in 4.6-m² plots. Spacing was 15 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Normal management practices were applied.

All entries had short-statured, nonlodging plants. Duration to 50% flowering was 60 to 77 d.

Yield differences among the entries were highly significant. Although 14 of the 36 cultivars registered more than 5 t/ha, 3 (IR29692-9-1-3-2, IR29725-76-3-3-2, and IR31851-6-3-3-3-2) recorded 7 t/ha (see table); 6.6 t/ha was registered by the highest yielding check, ADT36. Yields of the 3 cultivars were between 10% and 12.1% more than ADT36.

The three possess desirable plant types and long slender grain with consumer appeal. ☞

Performance of new early-duration IRRI cultivars at TNRRI, India.

Source	Cultivar	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)	% of ADT36
2443	IR25588-7-3-1	72	5.3	79.9
2444	IR25588-61-2-2	72	4.8	72.5
2446	IR25621-1-5-1-2	73	4.3	64.5
2447	IR25621-135-1-1	75	5.3	80.0
2449	IR25840-83-3-2	77	5.4	80.7
2460	IR28210-68-4-1-3-1	72	4.7	71.0
2465	IR29670-15-2-3	69	5.2	77.5
2466	IR29670-52-3-2-3	67	4.7	70.2
2469	IR29692-9-1-3-2	69	7.6	112.1
2470	IR29692-14-1-1-2	73	4.5	68.3
2471	IR29692-34-1-3-2-2	73	3.9	58.4
2472	IR29692-39-1-2-2-2	76	4.3	64.6
2473	IR29692-65-2-3-3	74	4.6	69.3
2474	IR29692-71-2-2-2	73	4.9	73.3
2477	IR29692-86-2-3-3	72	4.7	71.1
2478	IR29692-94-2-1-3	72	4.3	65.0
2479	IR29692-99-3-2-1	70	6.1	91.1
2481	IR29692-117-1-2-2	73	4.0	59.7
2484	IR29692-131-3-3-3	76	4.9	73.3
2487	IR29705-22-1-2-2	75	5.1	76.5
2489	IR29708-41-2-2-3	72	4.3	64.9
2490	IR29728-113-3-2-3	72	4.2	62.4
2491	IR29725-3-1-3-2	72	4.4	66.5
2493	IR29725-21-1-3-2	72	5.2	78.9
2494	IR29725-22-3-3-3	74	5.0	74.5
2497	IR29725-36-3-1-1	73	4.6	69.1
2500	IR29725-45-1-1-3	72	5.7	85.1
2501	IR29725-63-3-3-2	72	5.4	81.4
2502	IR29725-76-3-3-2	72	7.4	110.7
2505	IR29725-109-1-2-1	72	5.2	78.0
2506	IR29725-110-3-3-2	77	4.4	66.0
2511	IR29725-135-2-2-3	77	4.8	71.4
2536	IR31847-61-2-2-2-1	71	4.4	66.3
2540	IR31851-6-3-3-3-2	77	7.2	110.0
2541	IR31851-44-2-1-3-3	73	4.9	73.3
2543	IR31851-96-2-3-2-1	72	6.2	93.2
IR60		74	4.8	72.3
ADT36		75	6.6	100
TKM9		73	6.2	99.5
IR50		73	5.5	83.1
	CD 0.6 t/ha			
	CV 6.2			